

TEACHING PHILOSOPHY AND ITS ROLE IN EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the problems of teaching philosophy in higher educational institutions, understanding the role of philosophy in modern society and in the education system. It is shown that, despite the presence of philosophy as a compulsory discipline of the basic part of the curriculum, it can be stated that there is no holistic image of its teaching. In this regard, views are outlined on the search for new approaches to teaching philosophical disciplines, taking into account the specifics of philosophical knowledge

Keywords: competency-based approach, teaching philosophy, conceptual foundations for teaching philosophy, teaching philosophy abroad.

INTRODUCTION

The discussion about teaching philosophy in universities seems to me relevant for two main reasons: firstly, the question of the place of philosophy among the disciplines studied is increasingly subject to skepticism from not only students, but also teachers of non-core disciplines; secondly, the competency-based approach to modern education, focused on training a specialist in a specific field of knowledge, is aimed at “strengthening” the block of specialized disciplines at the expense of the humanities. Let's try to understand the problem by looking at it from different angles¹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The system of teaching philosophy at non-core faculties is traditionally propaedeutic in nature. Here the teacher faces the first difficulty. For example, how to convey to students the entire volume of centuries-old philosophical knowledge, which philosopher should be given preference in the analysis of a specific historical period, how to make philosophical language understandable to students? This series of questions can be continued, but it is precisely this that determines today the problems and prospects of turning to the philosophical heritage and its transmission to the student audience. When starting a course, you often have to deal with an attitude towards the subject as unnecessary and taking up part of the time for preparation in specialized disciplines. The time of

¹ Bidenko, V. I. (2016) Identification of the composition of competencies of university graduates as a necessary stage in the design of the new generation State Educational Standards of Higher Professional Education: method. allowance. M.: Inst. center for problems of quality of training of specialists. 72 p.

pragmatism has not passed over the student audience, and therefore approaches to teaching philosophy require a change in conceptual foundations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The change in the educational paradigm has led to an increased role for the student's practical training, and, as a result, there has been a shift towards increasing hours in specialized subjects at the expense of reducing the teaching of social sciences and humanities. The hierarchy of university disciplines is built according to their practical and application function, and therefore philosophy as theoretical knowledge does not seem to be a significant subject for representatives of the non-humanitarian community. An important role in this was played, among other things, by the loss of the ideological function of philosophy.

“Educational emphasis” is focused on preparing a student in a specific field of knowledge, on mastering a narrowly focused specialization. But a person is not a robot who mechanically performs his work. He lives in society, enters into communication with other people, and therefore, the scope of his vital interests is not limited to the scope of his professional activities. The disciplinary approach does not set itself the task of developing the graduate's ability to go beyond the limits of acquired knowledge in solving current applied problems. In my opinion, this approach is in many ways inferior to the interdisciplinary approach to education traditionally used for many years in Uzbekistan, since it is precisely this approach that contributes to the development of professional universalism, which implies variability in methods of activity and the ability to make situational decisions².

Can everyone be a philosopher?

Many teachers of non-philosophical disciplines agree with this phrase without doubt. This raises another question: “Can every teacher become a philosophy teacher?” Unfortunately, the positive answer for representatives of the non-philosophical community is also obvious. For example, ethics and applied ethics, philosophy of science and technology, philosophy of religion and religious studies are classified as philosophical disciplines according to the passport of scientific specialties. But what actually happens? These courses are taught by teachers, psychologists, doctors, etc., that is, by specialists who are not teachers of philosophical disciplines. This often leads to misunderstandings in the professional teaching community. A similar situation is typical for the discipline “History and Philosophy of Science,” which, at best, is divided into two

² Bryzgalina, E. V. (2010) Philosophy of education in the context of traditions and innovations // Man yesterday and today: interdisciplinary research. Vol. 4. M.: IFRAN. 248 p. pp. 3–18.

blocks, where the history of science is read by a representative of a particular scientific direction, and the philosophy of science is read by a representative of the philosophical community³. But this picture is also undergoing a change, and more and more often we have to admit that the course is completely given over to non-philosophical teachers. A similar situation is observed in the teaching of religious studies, which is also taught by cultural scientists, historians and, which is typical for our time, priests.

CONCLUSION

It is possible to increase interest in philosophy only if one goes beyond retelling the contents of textbooks. The philosophical and pedagogical course must be structured in such a way as to promote the student's reflection, his ability to make the transition from everyday to philosophical reasoning. This is possible in the case when the teacher, in a problematic presentation of the material, poses questions to students that motivate them to search for a solution, during which, in turn, new philosophical questions of a debatable nature would arise. Otherwise, "if you do not take any measures to undermine the infantile "evaluative position," but, on the contrary, encourage the presentation of the so-called "own opinion," then as a result, the rapid construction of a situational philistine, so to speak, worldview will begin "

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